

Synthesis, formation constants and biocidal activity of some bivalent transition metal complexes derived from *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadienphenylhydrazone

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Manuscript received 9 November 2003, revised 11 April 2005, accepted 5 August 2005

Abstract : Stability constants and thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) of complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} dichlorides with *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadienphenylhydrazone (CDOPH) have been determined in 50% (v/v) water-ethanol by measuring pH at different ionic strengths and temperatures. The stability constants have been calculated using Bjerrum's half \bar{n} integral method. The order has been found to be $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$. The metal complexes are screened for their antimicrobial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* at 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration in DMF. Two fungal strains *A. niger* and *C. albicans* are also examined.

Keywords : Synthesis, formation constants, biocidal activity, metal complexes.

Most of the studies reported on the hydrazones are centred around those derived from simple aldehyde and ketones¹. Present communication describes the synthesis and potentiometric studies of complex formation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadienphenylhydrazone (CDOPH). The ligand CDOPH has been synthesized by usual method reported in literature². Potentiometric studies are carried out in 50% water-ethanol media at 25°, 35° and 45 °C temperatures at ionic strengths of 0.05 and 0.10 *M* using Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti³.

Results and discussion

The proton-ligand stability constants and stability constants of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} dichloride complexes with *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadienphenylhydrazone as evaluated are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

The stability constants of complexes follows the order : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$. In the present investigations, it has been observed that the values of proton ligand constants (Table 1) decrease with increase in ionic strength of the medium and temperature. A similar trend in variation has been observed in the case of stability constants of metal complexes with CDOPH (Table 2).

Table 1. Proton-ligand constant of CDOPH 50% water-ethanol solution at different ionic strength and temperatures

Temp. (°C)	<i>I</i> (<i>M</i>)	<i>cis</i> -3,7-Dimethyl-2,6-octadienphenylhydrazone	
		log K_{H}	log K_{H_2}
25	0.05	10.60	5.82
	0.10	10.02	5.52
35	0.05	9.86	5.67
	0.10	9.55	5.05
45	0.05	8.89	4.88
	0.10	8.50	4.80

I = Ionic strength.

log K_{H} = Proton-ligand stability constant.

This type of behaviour has also been reported by several workers⁴. The values of stability constant (Table 2) reveal that these values decrease with increase in temperature along with $\text{p}K_{\text{a}}$ values. These results are in good agreement with those of Pitzer⁵. Thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH and ΔS indicate that the complex formation reactions are favourable at an ordinary temperature. The positive values of ΔS show the favourable conditions for formation of complexes. All the complexes are stable at room temperature. An examination of the elemental analysis of the complexes (Table 3) reveals the formation of 1 : 2 (Metal : Ligand) complexes. The IR spectra of *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadienphenylhydrazone exhibit sharp and strong bands at 3220, 1610 and 1275 cm^{-1} assigned

Table 2. Stability constants and thermodynamic functions for metal complexes of *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadienphenylhydrazone

Metal ion	Temp. (°C)	<i>I</i> (<i>M</i>)	Stability constant log <i>K</i>	-Δ <i>G</i> (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-Δ <i>H</i> (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>S</i> (kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
Co ^{II}	25	0.05	7.05	40.7	29.4	0.03
		0.10	6.98			
	35	0.05	7.01			
		0.10	6.82			
		0.10	6.71			
Ni ^{II}	25	0.05	7.51	44.0	30.5	0.04
		0.10	7.22			
	35	0.05	7.17			
		0.10	7.11			
		0.10	6.96			
Cu ^{II}	25	0.05	7.80	45.9	34.2	0.03
		0.10	7.52			
	35	0.05	7.45			
		0.10	7.31			
		0.10	7.24			
Zn ^{II}	25	0.05	7.25	42.2	35.6	0.02
		0.10	7.05			
	35	0.05	7.02			
		0.10	7.01			
		0.10	6.87			

log *K* are the values of stability constants calculated using Bjerrum's half \bar{n} integral method.

to as N-H, C=N and N-N vibrations respectively. The IR spectrum of ligand CDOPH exhibits intense bands at 1620 and 1575 cm⁻¹ due to νC=N and νC=C stretching respectively. The band at 945 cm⁻¹ is assigned to νN-N mode. Again the absorption in the region 335–360 nm is characteristic of phenylhydrazone (>N=N=C<) π-π* transition⁶, IR studies of the metal complexes with CDOPH clearly indicates that the coordination sites of ligand are nitrogen and π allylic bond⁷. The ligand CDOPH is coordinated to metals as neutral moiety. In complexes the absorption bands associated with ligand molecules suffered a blue shift indicative of coordination of ligand molecule with metal atom, retaining their hydrazone structure. Magnetic moment values (μ_{eff}) of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes at 25 °C are found to be 3.15, 2.85 and 1.78 B.M. respectively. Zn^{II} complex is diamagnetic in nature. All these values indicate spin free nature of these

metal ions are consistent with six coordinated octahedral geometry around the metal ion Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} (Table 3). The elemental analysis indicates that the composition of complexes is [ML₂Cl₂] where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} and L = CDOPH. The molar conductance of the metal complexes with CDOPH have been measured in DMSO, [complex], 1 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ indicating non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The electronic absorption spectrum of Co^{II} complex gives three distinct transitions at 8075 (8120), 16200 (16300) and 19600 (20100) cm⁻¹ which are assignable to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν₃). These bands are typical for high spin octahedral Co^{II} complex. The splitting of ν₃ bands into two or more components in Co^{II} complex is due to lifting of degeneracy of ⁴T_{1g} level either by the spin-orbital coupling or by presence of a low symmetry

Table 3. Elemental analysis and magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		M	C	H	N	
1.	CDOFH		78.9 (79.2)	8.8 (9.1)	10.8 (11.5)	-
2.	[Co(CDOFH) ₂ Cl ₂]	61.9 (62.5)	7.4 (7.2)	9.2 (9.1)	9.0 (9.5)	3.15
3.	[Ni(CDOFH) ₂ Cl ₂]	62.1 (62.5)	6.7 (7.2)	8.7 (9.1)	9.1 (9.5)	2.85
4.	[Cu(CDOFH) ₂ Cl ₂]	62.5 (62.0)	7.5 (7.1)	8.5 (9.0)	9.8 (10.2)	1.78
5.	[Zn(CDOFH) ₂ Cl ₂]	61.0 (61.8)	6.6 (7.1)	8.2 (9.0)	9.6 (10.5)	Diamag.

Table 4. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) in $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of CDOFH ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2$) and its metal complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	Bacteria		Fungi	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
1.	CDOFH	5.100	5.110	5.082	5.120
2.	[Co(CDOFH) ₂ Cl ₂]	0.972	0.925	0.981	0.986
3.	[Ni(CDOFH) ₂ Cl ₂]	0.975	0.973	0.965	0.965
4.	[Cu(CDOFH) ₂ Cl ₂]	0.228	0.280	0.116	0.116
5.	[Zn(CDOFH) ₂ Cl ₂]	0.233	0.119	0.241	0.211

component in the ligand field, however the ν_2/ν_1 ratio (2.12–2.15) also confirm the octahedral geometry. Spectrum of Ni^{II} complex exhibit three *d-d* transition bands at 10110 (10120), 16895 (16920) and 24750 cm^{-1} (24870 cm^{-1}) and are assignable to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ corresponding to ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 bands which shows its octahedral geometry. These spectral data can be utilized to compute the important ligand field parameters $10Dq$, β and λ using the ligand theory of spin allowed transition in d^8 configuration. The high values of $10Dq$ and β are consistent with the nitrogen coordination of the azomethine group⁸. The ratio of ν_2/ν_1 lies between 1.63 and 1.67 as expected for octahedral Ni^{II} complex. In electronic spectrum of Cu^{II} complex one broad assymmetric band at ~ 13555 – 14750 cm^{-1} corresponds to the transitions ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ supporting distorted octahedral geometry. The proposed geometry of Cu^{II} complex was further confirmed by the μ_{eff} value in the range of 1.74–1.78 B.M. Zinc(II) complex (d^{10} ion) is diamagnetic and doesn't show *d-d* transition. It has been reported that tetrahedral geometry is the most preferred structure for Zn^{II} complex⁹.

Biocidal activity :

Biocidal activity of a potentially active molecule is

altered on its complexation with a suitable metal ion because metals function as enzyme activators¹⁰. The antibacterial and antifungal activity of these compounds on selected bacteria *S. aureus* (Gram + ve) and *E. coli* (Gram -ve) and some fungi *A. niger* and *C. albicans* was carried out. The serial dilution method is used for testing antimicrobial activity of ligand CDOFH as well as its metal complexes. Culture media for growing bacteria consist of peptone, yeast extract, beef extract, dextrose an agar. pH is maintained at 6.5. Culture media for growing fungi consist of peptone, dextrose and agar. pH adjusted to 5.4 with suitable buffer.

The culture media used for slant and broth was sterilized by moist heat sterilization in an autoclave at 121°C using 15 lbs pressure for 15 min. Solutions of all the test compounds were prepared by dissolving 1 mg/ml of the substance in ethanol. All the solution were sterilized by passing through G-5 sintered glass crucible.

The observed results of Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MIC) of ligand CDOFH and its metal chelates (Table 4) reveal an enhancement of the antimicrobial activity of ligand in the form of its metal complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The re-

agent *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadienal (Citral-b) for the synthesis of ligand CDOPH was used as such (B.D.H.).

Preparation of ligand CDOPH :

It was synthesized by reported method².

Preparation of complexes :

An ethanolic solution of corresponding metal salt was added dropwise to the ethanolic solution of the ligand CDOPH in the molar ratio 1 : 2 (w/w) with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h and then cooled to room temperature. Complex crystals, dark red (cobalt), bluish green (nickel), brown (copper) and light yellow (zinc) were separated on cooling. These were washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo* over CaCl₂.

The IR spectra of ligand and metal complexes were recorded on a FTIR spectrophotometer model Magna-IR-550 NICOLET-USA in the range 4002–4225 cm⁻¹ employing KBr pellets. The electronic spectra were recorded on a Cary-14 spectrophotometer in DMF. Magnetic moments were measured by Gouy method.

A digital pH meter model 111E with a combined glass and calomel electrode assembly was used. The titrations were carried out at 25°, 35° and 45° (±0.1 °C). The molar ratio of metal to ligand was kept 1 : 5 in order to fulfill the maximum coordination number of the metal. The following solutions (total initial volume 50 ml) were titrated against a standard alkali KOH : (A) 1 ml of HClO₄ (0.05 M), (B) A + 2 ml of ligand (0.05 M), (C) B + 2 ml of metal salt (0.01 M). The ionic strength (0.05 and 0.10 M) was maintained by adding calculated amount of so-

dium perchlorate. Stability constants were calculated according to the procedure of Irving and Rossotti. The conductivity measurements were made on μ P based conductivity/TDS meter model 1601E using DMSO as a solvent.

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